

ASSESSMENT IN EFL CLASSES: PROBLEMS AND PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the analysis of the concept assessment and its implications into the real-life educational process. It is emphasized in the article that there is a strong necessity of redesigning instructions for objective assessment.

Key words: assessment, EFL, ESP, redesigning instructions, evaluation of language skills.

In the last few decades, it has been widely acknowledged that the benefits of education to society extended beyond the monetary domain. This observation is not new. In Ancient Greece, Plato and Aristotle identified the key role of education in contributing to personal fulfillment and social well-being. Research strongly supports this and has demonstrated that education as a proxy for 'human capital' not only provided individuals with the knowledge and skills to enhance their performance in the labour market and promote growth, but also contributed to socialization in modern societies by improving social capital defined as the complementary norms, values, attitudes and beliefs that govern interactions among people and institutions and predispose them to cooperation, mutual assistance and trust. [1]

Empirical evidence suggests that educational attainment nurtures people's social outcomes and promotes active participation in society and stability. However, it is unclear to what extent other types of human capital also correlate with social outcomes. In this way teachers sometimes cannot decide to what extent they should elaborate their assessment rubrics as well as techniques themselves. The main question here is "what we should pay attention to: knowledge or skills". On the one hand, this question does not seem to be serious as, certainly, giving an academic education our primary goal is to deliver knowledge. On the other hand, modern labour market requirements demand, mostly, a certain set of skills that are necessary for successful career. Therefore, the problem of assessment in EFL classes is rather topical here.

In Yerevan in May 2015, the Education Ministers identified four key priorities for the future:

1. enhancing the quality and relevance of learning and teaching;

2. fostering the employability of graduates throughout their working lives;
3. making our systems more inclusive;
4. implementing agreed structural reforms. [2]

Educators promoting student development as self-transformers create assignments which involve choices, explicitly related to an understanding of the contexts of the students. For example, students may choose to work in groups or individually. Students are able to choose from the choices provided or are able to come up with their own representation as long as it has been approved by the lecturer and meets the outcomes of the unit. It is assessed against the process of learning rather than just the product. For example, there may be a place where the students talk about what they learned from the assignment rather than what they got right in it. The rubric is related more to key ideas rather than particular content. [3]

In this case the urgent necessity to develop and re-structure the system of assessment in EFL classes claims for immediate measures, like elaboration of creative tasks that can help intellectual, creative, and critical skills of a student.

However, first, we should identify the concept assessment itself. For example, L.Bachman defined assessment as “a process of collecting information about something that we are interested in, according to procedures that are systematic and substantially grounded”. [4, p. 6-7] The result of an assessment procedure can be a score or a verbal description. Ari Huhta referred to assessment as “all kinds of procedures used to assess individuals (e.g., informal observations, self-assessments, quizzes, interviews, tests)”. [5, p. 469] Teachers assess their students every session. However, testing is a way of conducting assessment which is technically associated with definite timing and settled procedures. As A.Huhta defined “tests denote a particular type of formal, often carefully designed instruments”. [5, p. 469]

The very first use of language assessment is to make decisions for individuals (micro-evaluation), programs (macroevaluation), and other take-holders. [6] It can be used to select individuals, place them into appropriate course of study, make changes in instruction, predict future performance of test-takers, make changes in educational programs (formative or summative decisions), to formulate new research questions, and modify the understanding of a specific language phenomenon. [4] Therefore, the decision going to be made is so essential that it can define type of assessment.

Meanwhile, assessment is more apparent in the form of summative testing in educational world rather than informal formative tasks. Students look for ways to be the “top student” through assessment and they rarely try to see a connection between assessment and learning.

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